

Title of Impact Narrative: Improved spatial biodiversity priorities informs Ocean Governance in South Africa		
Target: (1) Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE); (2) Department of Mineral Resources and Energy (DMRE); (3) Transnet National Ports Authority ; (4) National Environmental Management, Biodiversity Act (NEMBA) implementing authorities; provincial conservation agencies; marine spatial planning practitioners; MPA planners, offshore industry operators; environmental NGOs; and coastal municipalities.		
Period when the underpinning research was undertaken: 2020-2026		
Details of staff conducting the underpinning research from the submitting unit:		
Name(s):	Role(s) (e.g. job title):	Period active:
Prof. Kerry Sink	Marine Programme Manager, SANBI	2020-2026
Megan van der Bank	Deputy Director, Marine Biodiversity Coordination, SANBI	2020-2026
Prideel Majiedt	Marine Research & Policy Advisor, SANBI	2020-2026
Nokubonga Mzimela	Research Assistant, SANBI	2025-2026
Period when the claimed impact occurred: 2025-2026		
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1 Summary of Outcome / Impact:

Through a participatory stakeholder process initiated in 2025, SANBI has updated its marine and coastal CBA Map with further steps planned over the longer term towards iterative improvement. Stakeholder dialogues with diverse audiences were convened in early 2026 to support data sharing and knowledge co-production. This participatory approach has supported the development of a CBA Map that is better understood, informed by the best available data and a co-developed path towards iterative updates with co-identified priorities. The consolidated set of updated priority areas will secure biodiversity through Environmental Impact Assessment screening, Marine Spatial Planning (MSP), participatory Marine Protected Area (MPA) planning and Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures (OECMs) and improved national reporting against the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP). (TRL 5–6 / SRL 4–5 to TRL 6 / SRL 5–6)

- Initiated an inclusive stakeholder dialogue process (January–February 2026) to co-develop an updated Marine CBA Map and priorities and paths for iterative improvement, marking a ***deliberate transition from spatial planning informed only by natural sciences to participatory biodiversity planning that seeks to include the knowledge, rights and values of diverse ocean users.***
- Two stakeholder dialogue sessions convened: an online session (103 participants) and an in-person session (64 participants), collectively engaging government (national, provincial and local), conservation sector, industry, indigenous people, local communities, small-scale fishers, recreational users, NGOs and academia, ***many participating in a CBA process for the first time.***
- Key co-identified priorities: integration of ***Indigenous Knowledge systems***; formal identification and inclusion of spatial areas used for small-scale fishing and customary practices; improved sectoral data for the cost layer; systematic spatial data coverage;

mapping and inclusion of culturally significant areas; climate resilience; and regular stakeholder report-back.

- Concerns and opportunities identified by stakeholders, from offshore energy and deep-sea mining to coastal communities, **reflecting the CBA Map's role as a cross-cutting biodiversity tool relevant to all ocean users** and regulators.
- A proposed process map for iterative CBA Map updating, translated into four languages (English, Afrikaans, IsiXhosa and IsiZulu), was co-reviewed and refined with stakeholder input — **establishing a foundation for an inclusive, multi-year update process**.
- **Expected outcomes:** Consolidated, robust and updated spatial biodiversity priorities for South Africa's mainland EEZ informed by diverse stakeholder inputs used by policy makers and managers for sound decision-making in national policy processes including MSP, MPA and OECM planning, EIA screening and NBSAP reporting.

2 Underpinning Research:

Context: South Africa's oceans face intensifying pressure from ocean use sectors. Meeting national and global biodiversity targets requires that decisions about where to develop, where to protect, and how to manage human activity are guided by reliable information (including natural and social science and indigenous knowledge). The Marine CBA Map is a critical tool used to guide decision-making in support of ocean sustainability.

Pre-Project Status: SANBI's Technical Guidelines for CBA Maps (Driver, Holness & Daniels, 2017) established the methodology for developing CBA maps. While this approach is mature in terrestrial systems, its translation to the marine environment required substantial additional work. The National Coastal and Marine Spatial Biodiversity Plan (Harris *et al.*, 2022) was the first comprehensive, national spatial biodiversity plan for South Africa's marine realm (v 1.2 of the Marine CBA map). Since 2022, new datasets, analyses and lessons have emerged, making updated CBA maps both necessary and timely.

Project Results: MISSION ATLANTIC has supported national advances in mapping species and ecosystems (Oliver *et al.*, 2022, Sink *et al.*, 2022, Sink *et al.*, 2023, Adams *et al.*, 2024 and MISSION ATLANTIC Deliverable D4.2 "[Seafloor characteristics and benthic communities across the Atlantic](#)") including Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (Franken 2025; Mission Atlantic Deliverable D4.2), improved understanding of ecological condition (SANBI 2025, Smit *et al.*, 2022, 2024, 2025 and **Mission Atlantic Deliverables D5.1 and D5.2**), improved mapping of sectors and pressures (Skein *et al.*, 2022, **Deliverables D3.2, D7.1, D7.2**), and knowledge exchange among scientists, policy makers, managers, industries and society, building the relationships needed for participatory spatial planning and management (Sink *et al.*, 2023, Rylands *et al.*, 2024, van der Bank *et al.*, 2025).

The research and engagements enabled through MISSION ATLANTIC have informed the science and stakeholder process for advancing v 1.3 *beta 1* of South Africa's CBA Map. Two stakeholder dialogue sessions enabled participatory planning with diverse stakeholders, built knowledge on CBA maps and their application, elicited stakeholder inputs, identified stakeholder priorities and concerns, and co-produced a roadmap for iterative updates over the longer term. A total of 144 stakeholders were engaged across 13 sectors. Key outcomes included co-identified priorities to improve technical work and stakeholder processes in future; a co-developed process map; recommendations for improving communication (e.g. simplified terminology, multilingual and multimedia materials, sector-specific engagements) and explicit recognition of the need to integrate Indigenous Knowledge systems, culturally significant areas and small-scale fishing grounds into future updates. The omission of these elements from previous CBA Map versions was raised consistently, reinforcing the view that equitable participation is essential for legitimate, fair and robust spatial planning products and processes.

The Marine CBA Map launched in 2022 (v1.2) was produced at TRL 5–6 / SRL 4–5. The methodology was technically validated and the map formally integrated into national planning systems (OCIMS, SEA processes, MSP, MPA planning), but participation of Indigenous Peoples, small-scale fishers and customary rights holders was limited, with consistent feedback identifying these gaps as a barrier to support and uptake.

This work directly builds on the National Biodiversity Assessment (SANBI 2025) and Mission Atlantic research—which together provide the most comprehensive and current synthesis of marine biodiversity knowledge and priority actions.

3 References to the research: (prioritise max 5 references that demo our academic credibility)

- Harris *et al.*, 2022. [A robust, systematic approach for developing the biodiversity sector's input for multi-sector Marine Spatial Planning](#). Ocean & Coastal Mngmnt. 10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2022.106368
- Sink *et al.*, 2026. Shaping the process to update South Africa's Marine Map of Critical Biodiversity Areas and Ecological Support Areas: Draft Report from the CBA Map Dialogues. South African National Biodiversity Institute, 41 pp. <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12143/9586>
- Sink *et al.*, 2023. [Iterative mapping of marine ecosystems for spatial status assessment, prioritization, and decision support](#). Frontiers in Ecology & Evolution 10.3389/fevo.2023.1108118
- Skein *et al.*, 2022. [Scoping an integrated ecosystem assessment for South Africa](#). Frontiers in Marine Science 10.3389/fmars.2022.975328
- Smit *et al.*, 2025. [Depth and habitat drive spatial patterns in fish functional diversity: a trait-based assessment across South Africa and southern Mozambique](#). Marine Environmental Research 10.1016/j.marenvres.2025.107620
- South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI). 2025. National Biodiversity Assessment 2025: The status of South Africa's biodiversity - Website. South African National Biodiversity Institute (an entity of the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment), Pretoria. <https://nba.sanbi.org.za/>

4 Details of the IMPACT NARRATIVE:

The CBA Map updated in 2026 (v 1.3 beta 1) represents the beginning of a longer-term participatory planning process in South Africa. The CBA Map is a foundational knowledge product currently sought after by the national Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment to help guide several spatial planning and policy processes. The CBA Map is poised to support informed decision-making based on reliable science and diverse stakeholder inputs.

WHO & ROLE: The two stakeholder dialogue sessions were convened by SANBI and facilitated by Megan van der Bank (SANBI) and Loyiso Dunga, with presentations by Prof. Kerry Sink (SANBI), Prideel Majiedt (SANBI), and Dr Stephen Kirkman (DFFE Oceans & Coasts). Underpinning technical mapping was supported by Nokubonga Mzimela (SANBI) and Mari-Lise Franken (SANBI, UCT) with analyses to support spatial biodiversity prioritisation conducted by a consultant (Dr Linda Harris, NMU). Diverse stakeholders participated in the process to date including conservation entities and NGOs, government (including the national government department tasked with ocean governance in South Africa), Indigenous Peoples (e.g., the Westcoast Guriqua San Council and CONTRALESA), small-scale fishers, offshore energy operators (TotalEnergies, Shell), academia and independent consultants. Funding for the online session and consultant fees (for analyses) was provided by the EU Horizon 2020 Mission Atlantic Project; the in-person session was co-funded by The Nature Conservancy — reflecting broad international and civil society investment in this process.

Figure 1. The previous CBA Map (v1.2) launched in 2022, updated based on MISSION ATLANTIC new knowledge and mapping (see Harris *et al.* 2026 for high-resolution version of the map).

WHEN & EVIDENCE OF ENGAGEMENT: The online stakeholder dialogue (27 January 2026, 103 participants) and in-person dialogue (12 February 2026, 64 participants) together represent a significant advancement towards inclusive and meaningful stakeholder participation around South Africa's Marine CBA Map. Participant lists, attendance registers, Google Form responses, Menti poll results, breakout group notes, and a draft report (Sink *et al.*, 2026) provide traceable, public-domain evidence of the scope and depth of engagements. The updated CBA Map (v1.3 beta 1) produced.

VALUE & ADDED BENEFITS: The CBA Map is sought after by the national government department responsible for South Africa's sustainable ocean management. CBA Map is of importance to Marine Protected Areas (MPA) planning, as an input into MSP biodiversity sector plans and national planning and reporting as part of the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan. CBA Map updates are highly likely to support policy processes in future.

South Africa has committed to support the Kunming-Montreal [Global Biodiversity Framework Target 3 "Conserve 30% of Land, Waters, and Seas"](#). Government dialogue towards MPA planning has commenced but currently South Africa lacks a consolidated set of spatial marine biodiversity priorities based on the best available science to guide these dialogues. The CBA Map and its updates, will serve to fill this gap. Several other GBF targets will be supported including GBF Target 1 "[Plan and Manage all Areas To Reduce Biodiversity Loss](#)" around participatory, integrated and biodiversity inclusive spatial planning. This body of work will support reporting against several of South Africa's NBSAP targets.

Currently, South Africa is using the CBA Map (v1.2, 2022) in its ongoing MSP process. This body of work will enable MSP to proceed with the most up to date set of biodiversity priorities available for inclusion in analyses.

At present, marine biodiversity priority areas are not adequately considered in EIAs because these priorities are not yet included in South Africa's screening tool and are not socialized amongst EIA practitioners. After iterative updates, the CBA Map will feed into the national EIA screening tool alongside terrestrial biodiversity priorities. This will allow practitioners and

regulators to conduct assessments and make decisions that are scientifically sound and based on the best available biodiversity data.

The participatory approach used to produce CBA Map v1.3 beta 1 and planned future process steps will allow for more and diversified data sharing, collective goal setting, participatory scenario planning and allow stakeholders to feel part of the planning process, promoting uptake.

FIT FOR PURPOSE & LONG-TERM UPTAKE: Fitness for purpose is demonstrated through the iterative, co-designed nature of the update process itself. A proposed process map was co-developed with stakeholders for CBA map v 1.3 — establishes a transparent, multi-stage pathway for on-going participation, from data calls and beta map reviews to sector-specific engagements and final validation. The process is explicitly designed to generate multiple successive versions of the updated CBA map, each strengthened by successive rounds of stakeholder input — ensuring durability and relevance well beyond any single project or funding cycle. Long-term uptake will depend on sustained human and financial resources, particularly to support the **meaningful participation of historically marginalised stakeholder groups including Indigenous Peoples and small-scale fishers.**

Collectively, the two CBA dialogue sessions held in early 2026 have supported the relational and methodological foundation for an updated Marine CBA Map that is technically robust, transparently developed, publicly available (open-access), socially equitable and broadly understood, positioning South Africa to meet its international biodiversity commitments through an ocean governance approach grounded in inclusive, participatory science.

Figure 2. Process map for iterative update of South Africa’s marine and coastal CBA map co-developed with stakeholders.

5. Sources/ Evidence to corroborate the impact:

- Sink KJ, Mzimela NZ, van der Bank MG, Majiedt PA, Dunga LV, and Kirkman SP. 2026. Shaping the process to update South Africa's Marine Map of Critical Biodiversity Areas and Ecological Support Areas : Draft Report from the CBA Map Dialogues. South African National Biodiversity Institute, 41 pp. <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12143/9586>. *Stakeholder dialogue feedback report (SANBI, 2026) — synthesis of outcomes, priorities, and next steps from the January–February 2026 CBA stakeholder dialogue series. To be released publicly after participant inputs are received on draft report by 15 April 2026.*
- SANBI Marine CBA Spatial Datasets — publicly accessible via SANBI's Biodiversity GIS portal (bgis.sanbi.org): downloadable CBA map layers, classification methodology documentation, and associated NBA technical reports.
- National Biodiversity Assessment 2025 released- [Media Statement NBA 2025 9 December 2025.pdf](#) – *the marine component drew from research conducted under MISSION ATLANTIC.*
- Marine NBA 2025 website- [Overview](#)- *contains pages with progress in ecosystem mapping, threat status assessment, condition, and priority actions and areas (the latter around CBAs).*
- National NBSAP reporting [Online Reporting Tool](#)- *By 2036, expand and conserve coastal and marine areas by 100 000 ha (10%) marine protected areas and 50 000 ha (5%) OECMs (including estuaries); By 2030, ensure that: (1) 100% of Spatial Development Frameworks (SDFs), Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and Estuarine Management Plans incorporate systematic biodiversity plans.*
- Strategic Environmental Assessment for Offshore Wind Energy (Phase 1 and 2, 2021–2023) — technical reports reference CBA classifications in determining spatial exclusion and caution zones. Available: <https://share.google/nHqV9ZhKVb8ywbuPD>.
- MSP gazette for public input March 2023- [Marine Spatial Planning Act: Marine Sector Plans: Comments invited](#)- *with area plan development ongoing.*

TESTIMONIALS by Stakeholders in position of influence:

Dr Gerhard Cilliers, Director of Marine Biodiversity Research, at DFFE, Oceans & Coasts (16 Feb 2026)

*“The coastal and marine Critical Biodiversity Areas Map (CBA v1.2) map integrates vast amounts of relevant spatial information on ecosystems, species, ecological processes and human activities to identify priority biodiversity areas where biodiversity loss needs to be avoided or where biodiversity needs to be restored... and its associated sea-use guidelines provided **the basis for the Marine Biodiversity Sector Plan for MSP, a plan that was co-developed with MBR**”.*

Chief Ferdienand Fransman, Protocol Spokesperson for the WestCoast Guriqua San Council *“We value the collaborative efforts on biodiversity issues as specially on Critical Biodiversity Areas...Future engagement are crucial to share knowledge and protect our resources...A broader platform with focus group meetings would be effective in sharing information and recognizing indigenous contributions”.*

Edward Groenewald, HSE Sustainability Manager, TotalEnergies (South Africa): *requests dedicated Oil and Gas sector collaboration in 2026, to target individual license rights holders to discuss individual biodiversity data and conservation needs per license offshore block (comms 19 Feb 2026).*

Charlotte Boyd, Regional Conservation Programme Manager, and **Kirsten Day**, Programme Manager: Policy and Advocacy; **BirdLife South Africa**: *“By pinpointing areas of high biodiversity importance, South Africa's coastal and marine CBA map provides essential information to support biodiversity-inclusive spatial planning... consistent with Target 1 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Up-to-date spatial information on coastal and marine CBAs is critical for integrating safeguards for areas of high biodiversity importance into marine spatial planning and to address site-level planning and decision-making (e.g., on marine protected area (MPA) delineation, recognition of other effective area-based conservation measures (OECMs)...while enabling sustainable development of blue economic sectors”.*

EVIDENCE OF POLICY CITATIONS:

- [Ocean & Coasts, Annual Science Report No. 22](#) (Gov. South Africa)
Gov. South Africa, 18 May 2023

A robust, systematic approach for developing the biodiversity sector's input for multi-sector Marine Spatial Planning

Linda R. Harris et al. (2022) *Ocean & Coastal Management*

Harris L, Holness S, Kirkman S, Sink K, Majiedt P, Driver A. 2022. South Africa's National Coastal and Marine Spatial Biodiversity Plan: biodiversity priorities for marine spatial planning. 12th Western Indian Ocean Marine Science Association WIOMSA Symposium, Gqeberha, South Africa, 10-15 October 2022.

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- [A review of the state of the coast of KwaZulu-Natal](#) (Gov. South Africa)
Gov. South Africa, Ministry of Environmental Affairs, 28 Jul 2022

Iterative mapping of marine ecosystems for spatial status assessment, prioritization, and decision support

Kerry J. Sink et al. (2023) *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*

Sink, K.J, Harris, L.R., Skowno, A., Livingstone, T., Franken, M., Atkinson, L.J., Bernard, A., Porter, S., Cawthra, H., Currie, J., Dayaram, A., De Wet, W., Dunga, V., Filander, Z., Green, A., Herbert, D., Karenyi, N., Palmer, R., Pfaff, M., Makwela, M., McKay, F., Van Niekerk, L., Van Zyl, W., Bessinger, M., Holness, S., Kirkman, S.P., Lamberth, S. and Lück-Vogel, M., 2019b. Marine Ecosystem Classification and Mapping. In: Sink, K., van der Bank, M., Majiedt, P., Harris, L., Atkinson, L., Kirkman, S. and Karenyi, N., eds.. South African National Biodiversity Assessment 2018 Technical Report Volume 4: Marine Realm. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria, South Africa, 1-65 pp.

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- Book: [Hydrofeminist Thinking With Oceans](#) (Chapter: When ancestors are included in ocean decision- and meaning-making) cites Haris et al., 2026

ABSTRACT

The intangible nature of many forms of ocean-associated heritage and knowledge in South Africa makes it challenging to incorporate them into legal proceedings, and so they are often excluded in various forms of formal/legal ocean decision-making.

In this chapter, through the use of a public storytelling methodology, and call and response methods, developed by creative collective “Empatheatre”, an animation entitled “Indlela Yokuphila: The Soul’s Journey” encapsulated the sacred journey of the soul in a Zulu belief system, and how it is enmeshed with the hydrological cycle, and the deep sea. This approach to representing, and including other ways of knowing the ocean, opened up bigger questions around ocean education and the knowledge hierarchies (and evidence hierarchies that exist in our legal and educational structures).

6. Impact Pathway for 2026-2030:

- 2026: External Evaluation of Impact, by Saskia Walcott (Walcott Communications)
- 2026: Official updates of CBA Map v1.3 used by DFFE, South Africa & evidence of added value
- 2027: Follow-up Testimonials by TotalEnergies (South Africa) on *biodiversity data and conservation needs per license offshore block*.

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